

The Role of Constraints in Entropy Part 2

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We have argued in previous notes that both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions are linked to the constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$, where $f(e_i) = e_i$ (or $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ in the Tsallis case.) Given that multiple $\{p(e_i)\}$ sets satisfy these constraints, one may obtain a minimum information set by creating a function (entropy) G whose differential contains no more information than the constraints. In other words $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$, where $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ or $\sum_i p(e_i)^q h(p(e_i))$ in the Tsallis case.

In Part I, we tried to reconcile this approach with the reaction balance $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ and $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ approach which may be used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for an ideal gas. Here we present a different approach linking the two by considering $p(e_i)$ in the constraints being replaced with $p(e_{i1})p(e_{j2})$ (sum over i, j), i.e the usual procedure used for finding the entropy of two systems (and showing it is additive in the MB case). Here, we apply this approach to the constraint and argue that it is the constraint behaviour which governs the additivity -non-additivity behaviour of entropy in these two cases.

We next note that even though $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ is a possible physical constraint, another physical constraint is $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = F$. This second constraint collapses to the first when $q=1$, but is non-additive when $p(e_{1i}) \rightarrow p(e_{1i})p(e_{1j})$. In this case, one has non-additive entropy because of the behaviour of the constraint. Furthermore, this leads to a relation between the Tsallis form of $h(p(e_i))$ and the MB $h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$.

Reaction Balance and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution was developed long before the Tsallis (and Kaniadakis and other forms) and has been studied extensively. As a result, some specific features linked to this distribution seem to have become regarded as perhaps universal truths about entropy and statistical systems. In particular, one has the additivity of entropy and the physical idea of reaction balance (at least for an ideal gas):

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) seems to follow from physical ideas (although it is an idealization and approximation). In other words, one might argue that there is no need for an entropy function (and its maximization subject to constraints) because ((1a)) and ((1b)) yield the distribution and are physical statements.

In Part 1, we tried to link ((1a)) and ((1b)) to the idea of an entropy function G , whose:

$$dG = 0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i) \quad ((2))$$

Here, we provide a second approach based on $\sum_i p(e_i) \rightarrow \sum_{i,j} p(e_{1i}) p(e_{2j})$

Consider: $\sum_i (e_{1i}+e_{2j}) p(e_{1i})p(e_{2j}) = \sum_i e_i p(e_i) + \sum_j e_j p(e_j)$ ((3))

In other words, the constraint is additive and this makes the entropy additive.

Next, consider:

$\sum_{i,j} (e_{1i}+e_{2j}) d(p(e_{1i})p(e_{2j})) = \sum_i (e_{1i} dp(e_{1i})) p(e_{2j}) + \sum_j e_{2j} dp(e_{2j}) p(e_{1i}) + \sum_{i,j} (e_{1i}) p(e_{1i}) dp(e_{2j}) + \sum_{i,j} (e_{2j}) dp(e_{2j}) p(e_{1i})$ ((4))

Given that $\sum_i d(p(e_i)) = 0$, the last two terms on the RHS are 0. If

$G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ ((5)), this result implies that:

$h[p(e_{1i})p(e_{2j})] = h(p(e_{1i})) + h(p(e_{2j}))$ ((6))

Given that: $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((7)) by definition of the method of constraints ((2))

$h(p(e_1+e_2)) = ((6))$ or $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ ((8))

((8)) immediately suggests a power law distribution, i.e yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

One may immediately note that ((8)) implies that: $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ ((9))

if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$.

((9)) is the usual reaction balance condition which follows directly from analysis of the differential for the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. Thus, it seems to be a general result which does not depend on two body scattering as the MB distribution may be applied to a two energy level atom. The constraint:

$\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((10))

Is really a statement about the average energy of a system and not necessarily the distribution mechanism of this energy. In the case of an ideal gas, one may introduce a two body elastic scattering model which is consistent with ((10)) and the $dG=0$ result and actually bypasses $dG=0$ through ((1a)) and ((1b)), but this is a specific model and not the norm, as argued in Part I.

The Tsallis Scenario

One sometimes finds the Tsallis approach introduced mathematically in the following way. Consider the math identity:

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{1}{1-q} \{ 1 - p(e_i)^{1-q} \} = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((11))$$

The argument then seems to be that given the MB entropy function: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, one may introduce an analogous entropy:

$$\text{Tsallis entropy: } \sum_i p(e_i)^q (1 - p(e_i)^{1-q}) / (1-q) = \sum_i \frac{1}{1-q} (1 - p(e_i)^q) \quad ((12))$$

This seems to be a purely mathematical approach. We have argued that MB and Tsallis entropy are based on information related to constraints and so it is the constraints which contain the physics and essentially create the entropy in these two cases. Although $p(e_i)$ is a very common probability form in problems, it is possible to have a cycling situation. In particular, at the beginning of the first unit of a set of q (q being a positive integer), one has $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, where $p(e_i)$ has some physical interpretation. At the beginning of the next cycle, one again starts from the condition $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. This holds for each cycle, up to q , so the product probability for each e_i is:

$$p(e_i)^q \text{ and this is unnormalized } ((13))$$

((13)) is completely physical and is a generalization of $p(e_i)$ as one obtains $p(e_i)$ for $q=1$. Thus, based on a physical constraint scheme, one may introduce the Tsallis entropy we argue. We have argued that the entropy function is based on the constraints and so if the entropy is not additive, it really means that this follows from the constraints not being additive. In particular,

$$\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = F \quad ((14))$$

is not additive and so leads to a Tsallis entropy which is not additive. Having a non-additive entropy is not particularly unusual or problematic, we argue.

In addition, the math identity ((11)) follows from the constraint approach as well because:

$$\text{MB Case: } p(e_i) \frac{dh(p)}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \text{ or } h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((15a))$$

$$\text{Tsallis case } p(e_i)^q \frac{dh(p)}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \rightarrow h(p(e_i)) = C_1 + p(e_i)^{1-q} \quad ((15b))$$

For $q=1$, ((15b)) should become $\ln(p)$, and so one may establish the identity ((11)), but physically it is the constraint ((14)) which is the physical driver of the Tsallis approach, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that reaction balance linked with an ideal gas case, i.e. $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((B)), follows from the $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ approach of creating an entropy function G . In particular, we show that one way to

obtain it is to replace $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ with $\sum_{i,j} p(e_{1i})p(e_{2j}) h(p(e_{1i})p(e_{2j}))$. This then leads to general results for $h(p(e_i))$ for the MB case. Thus, ((B)) which physically describes elastic two-body collisions in an ideal gas is a special case of a more general entropy approach, as argued in Part I.

We argue that the constraint approach puts the entire focus on the constraint. Thus, a more general and physical constraint than $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i$ is $\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i$, which collapses to the former for $q=1$. We argue that $p(e_i)^q$ is physical in nature. We further note that this constraint is not additive for $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_{1i}) p(e_{2j})$ and so the entropy in turn is not additive. Thus, it is the constraint which explains the nonadditive nature of entropy. We finally argue that based on the physical $p(e_i)^q$ constraint, one may create the Tsallis entropy and obtain the math identity ((11)).